

Interview Protocol

Paper: Creative Problem-Solving: A Study with Blind and Low Vision Software Professionals

Part 1: General Questions about Job

1. Would you tell me about your current/most recent job: daily job duties as a <job title>?
2. What kind of tools do you use for work? What tasks do you use them for?
3. What kinds of assistive technologies or resources do you use to access information at work?
4. What are some resources you reach out to when you face accessibility barriers at work?
5. Do you disclose your disability at work?
6. Do you have any social strategies or tricks you use when you face accessibility problems at work?

Part 2: Workarounds

1. Do you use any off-the-shelf technologies as workarounds for accessibility barriers at work?
2. Have you ever built technical solutions to make your work life easier or workaround inaccessible tools and tasks?
3. Did the tool you built ever yield unexpected results?
4. Did you build these tools during your work hours?
5. What are your reasons for building these tools?
6. Have you ever used tools or plugins that another blind and low vision person or an ally has built and released?
7. Are you aware of communities of software professionals who are blind or have low vision?
8. Could you tell me about the activities you engage in with those communities?
9. What do you think about communities that exist (like program-I) for BLVSPs?